

Teacher's feedback using Moodle and blend learning

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Abstract

This report based on our experience and collected data explain the useful teacher's feedback, which are received from implementing blend learning through creating online e-training course, multimedia e-books, self-assessment tests and etc., on Moodle online learning management system. The sites of e-learning of Microbiology, Chemistry, Ecology and Biochemistry were among the first developed and used for full and part time study in blend learning. The obtained feedback that has been registered is proper and entire information about student process of learning; higher quality of acquired knowledges; better and low cost support for student training; adequate students assessment and efficacy in applying e-test for exam.

Keywords: web learning resources, Moodle, blend learning, student assessment, teachers feedback

1. Introduction

The blend learning is extensively applied nowadays as perhaps the most prominent delivery mechanism in higher education, business, government, and military setting (Bonk & Graham, 2006), and it is described as implementation of an ICT environment that expands classroom to the virtual ICT reality (Pardo-Gonzalez, 2013).

Pure distance learning loses social group part of study and that have negative impact on student motivation toward acquisition of new information and that cannot be an institution aim (Krake, 2013). The blend learning support, reinforce and enhance learning potential of students (Pardo-Gonzalez, 2013); it is the opportunity to integrate the innovative and technological advantages offered by online learning with the best of traditional learning (Thorne, 2003). Moreover, in blend learning learners create better organize information through more and richer connections between the new and old information that they already knew (Douglas & Paton, 2013). Therefore blend learning allows the learner to retain more of what is learned (Bonk & Graham, 2006).

2. Blend learning in Faculty of Technics and Technology - Yambol, Trakia University – Stara Zagora

The e-learning using Moodle in Faculty of Technics and Technology - Yambol, Trakia University – Stara Zagora starts at 2005 with the project "Distance learning in Bulgaria. Opportunities for treatment at the Technical College - Yambol." Many other projects after that developed reach data base with supporting e-learning materials ("Creating and piloting a methodology for e-learning at the Technical College-Yambol"; "Intellectual systems and technologies in e-learning"; "Improving the quality of teaching using multimedia products and systems"; "Multimedia training course in Microbiology and opportunities for transition to e-learning"; etc.).

Among the first developed e-courses were Ecology, Chemistry, Biochemistry, Microbiology, Informatics and etc. (<http://tk.uni-sz.bg/edutk/>). The influence of them on the quality of study had been previously reported (Slavova et al., 2009; Dineva&Nedeva, 2009; Dineva&Stoikova 2011; Dineva&Ducheva, 2011). Today after implementation of blended learning as a regular method for teaching there exists large data base organized as Thracian e-University (fig.1), with e-courses that covered almost all disciplines in the curriculums, using Moodle learning platform (<http://edu.uni-sz.bg/>).

Fig. 1 Thracian e-University

With the a new e-data base students have the opportunity to use free of charge multimedia e-books overlying different subjects (fig.2), e-virtual library, e-presentations, e-quizzes and on-line assessment of their knowledges, academic schedule, chats and forums, and site for an accurate and useful student information.

Fig. 2 Multimedia e-book of Biochemistry created with EU-project – in Thracian e-University

In Trakia University the students and teachers have the opportunity to be registered online at the existing data base, www.trakia-uni.bg and to have access to a personal e-mail and Integrated Management and Information System (Nedeva&Karabaliev, 2017).

3. Teacher's feedback using Moodle and blend learning

According to Klompaker, (2016), online learning programs as Moodle allow teachers to set up calendars, quizzes and assignments, track student logins and work progress, make announcements, make blog posts and much more. All in all, the feedback for teachers as well as for learners from blend learning is positive (Krake, 2013).

The process of blend allowed being received feedback in face of correcting and improving the learning content in the cycles of its implementation (fig.3, Pardo-Gonzalez, 2013). We also registered the enhancement of students' motivation to study and willingness to help in improving learning content and correcting eventual technical errors.

Fig. 3. Stages of the incorporation process of the blend (Pardo-Gonzalez, 2013)

Using e-quizzes on Moodle permit teachers to track student attempts and success in the process of learning (fig.4), that also gives precise and reliable information about the stage of understanding and assimilation of supporting study e-materials, as well as the possibility to improve learning data info. According to Lee-Post (2009), the success of e-learning depends on *systems design* - evaluated by quality of information, system, and service; on *delivery* - evaluated along one success factor: use; and *outcome analysis* - evaluated on user satisfaction, and net benefits. It is proved that e-learning better enabled students to manage where and when to learn, and spent less time for study (Lee-Post, 2009). The teachers' feedback is to have powerful tool to monitoring and improved the weakness points of students' knowledges.

Fig. 4. Numbers of Attempts in self-examining test

Absolutely all mentors using remote technologies in process of teaching have assessed that method of training as perspective and efficient to provide sufficient knowledges to the users (Kuznetsov, 2017). On fig.5 is given the results of students' achievements as grate report, after using e-materials for study and training.

Fig. 5. Students achievement grade report – Moodle statistics

Usually after one semester of Moodle usage, students are feeling very comfortable with the system (Hölbl&Welzer, 2010). Consequently, there is no more negative impacts on student e-assessment that can be caused from lack of enough knowledge and training of computer and other ICT use. Shivacheva-Pineda (2017) also confirmed the efficacy in applying e-test for exam control, based on monitoring the results in period of 2013 to 2016 and comparing the results of various different forms of assessment.

Conclusion

The proved feedback of teachers using Moodle and its possibilities are proper and entire information about student learning process; better acquired knowledges with higher quality; low cost support of student training; adequate, fast and powerful students' assessment; efficacy and efficiency in applying e-test for student assessment.

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